

Soil physical and chemical properties of several soil order in suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The appropriate management of suboptimal dryland expands potentially agricultural areas because the soil properties in such an area are very diverse in each region and agroclimatic zone. A field study and laboratory analysis have been carried out to assess soil chemical characteristics in several soil orders in suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District, Indonesia. There are five soil orders representing soil types in the areas, namely Inceptisol Blang Bintang, Andisol Saree, Mollisol Krueng Raya, Ultisol Jantho, and Oxisol Lembah Seulawah. Samples were taken for each horizon layer from the soil orders. Analyses of the soil physical and chemical properties were done, including texture, pH (in H₂O and KCl), organic C, total N, total P₂O₅ and K₂O contents, available P, exchangeable base cations (Ca-, Mg-, K-, and Na-exch), potential cation exchange capacity (CEC), Al- and H-exch., base saturation (BS), and electrical conductivity (EC). The results showed that soil physical properties and chemical characteristics varied between soil orders, but soil fertility status in some soil orders was predominantly low. This low fertility status is indicated by acid soil reaction (pH 5.25–6.48), low total C (<10 g/kg), low total N (0.7–2.7 g/kg), and low of bases saturation (<40%), so that these soils require the addition of soil amendments and fertilizers. Soil orders with low soil fertility are Oxisols, Ultisols, and Inceptisols, while other soil orders such as Andisol and Mollisol are classified as medium soil fertility. The order of soil quality from the highest to lowest is: Mollisols = Andisols > Ultisols = Oxisols = Inceptisols.

Keywords: suboptimal dryland, soil order, soil chemical properties, fertility constraints

INTRODUCTION

A suboptimal land is a land that has low soil productivity and fertility, rendering it unable to support optimal plant growth. In general, the suboptimal land is divided into two typologies: dryland and wetland. In Indonesia, the area

of dryland reaches 144.5 million hectare (ha), and most of them belong to acidic mineral soils because of their pH of less than 5.5 (Sufardi 2012). The most extensive spread of acidic drylands is found in 3 major islands, namely Kalimantan, Sumatera, and Papua. Most of the sub-optimal dryland require the appropriate technology to improve their agricultural qualities (Lakitan and Gofar, 2013).

In Aceh Province, the potential for dryland for agriculture is still vast, reaching 1,154,445 ha. According to BPS Aceh Besar (2013), 79,238 ha of dryland are utilized potentially for agriculture in Aceh District which consists of the rest of the land functions as non-irrigated rice fields (6,946 ha), moorland area (46,761 ha), fields (21,892 ha), and abandoned land (3,639 ha). Based on the vastness of the area, the suboptimal dryland in Aceh Province is considered as a potential natural resource for agricultural development, especially in increasing yields of food crops, horticulture, and plantations in order to maintain national food demands. Its potential is capable of strengthening Indonesian food security. However, despite having been developed since 1985 by implementing various technological innovations, the results are still not optimum compared to the production plants on rice fields.

The main problem of dryland areas for agriculture improvement is low soil fertility caused by some chemical constraints that limit plant growth, such as soil acidity and nutrient availability. According to Abdurachman *et al.* (2008), dryland generally has low soil fertility, and low organic matter content. This condition is exacerbated by the limited use of organic fertilizers, especially in seasonal food crops. Furthermore, the levels of soil organic matter in the tropics are rapidly decreasing naturally, reaching 30-60% within ten years (Suriadikarta *et al.*, 2002). Also, carbon elements from organic bonds are converted to carbon dioxide by microorganisms which decreases gradually soil organic matter (Stevenson, 2010; FAO, 2005; Sposito, 2008).

Another problem on dryland is low soil pH. Many soils in wet tropical climate are found to be acidic, especially those belonging to the soil orders of Ultisols, Oxisols, Inceptisols, Andisols, and Spodosols (Sanchez, 2010), which are often referred to as irregularly charged acidic mineral soils (Uehara and Gillman, 1981). These soils are characterized by low soil pH (pH <6.5), low soil CEC, low base content, and high phosphate fixation (Sanchez, 2010). Sufardi *et al.* (2017) reported that most of drylands have low organic C content, low total N, low base saturation, and low cation nutrient availability, low soil CEC, and low available P (Helmi *et al.*, 2017; Martunis *et al.*, 2017). However, research conducted by Husni *et al.* (2016) in Pidie district resulted that some drylands turned out to have a high soil CEC (> 35 cmol/kg) and very high available P (> 40

mg/kg). The results of these studies indicate that soil chemical characteristics in dryland depend on the level of soil type, climate, and soil management.

Although general information about the constraints and soil fertility status in dryland farming systems has been widely known, the specific information on each soil type and the agroclimatic zone is limited. Therefore, a field observation is indispensable to obtain data of soil physical and chemical characteristics on dryland farming systems. This study aims to determine the physical properties and soil chemical characteristics and evaluate soil fertility status in several soil orders in the suboptimal dryland in Aceh Besar District, Indonesia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was carried out in Aceh Besar District, Aceh Province (Indonesia) in five pedons from several soil orders representing suboptimal dryland, which can be potentially developed as food crops. The study began in May until August 2018. The soil orders were identified through morphological observations, determination of the characteristic horizons of each profile of soils, and laboratory analysis. Field observation techniques and soil type nomenclature are based on the USDA soil classification system (Soil Survey Staff, 2014). Five soil orders that used in the study were Inceptisols (Oxic Haplustept) Blang Bintang (S1), Andisols (Eutric Hydrudand) Saree (S2), Oxisols (Plinthic Kandiodox) Lembah Seulawah (S3), Mollisols (Typic Calcisquoll) Krueng Raya (S4), and Ultisols (Typic Kandiaquoll) Jantho. Each horizon was taken about one kilograms of soil samples to analyze soil physical and chemical properties in laboratory.

The soil analysis of physical and chemical properties included soil texture (pipette method), soil pH, total C and N, total of P₂O₅ and K₂O, available P, exchangeable cations of Ca, Mg, K, and Na, cation exchange capacity (CEC), exchangeable Al and H, and electrical conductivity (EC). The soil pH was measured in H₂O and 1M KCl suspensions (1: 2.5). Organic C was determined by Walkley and Black method through wet destruction with H₂SO₄ and K₂CrO₇ solution. Total N was determined using Kjeldahl method while the P₂O₅ and K₂O were extracted with 25% HCl reagent. Available P was analyzed using Bray II method (0.25 N HCl + 0.30 N NH₄F). P in the 25% HCl extract and Bray II were measured by spectrophotometer, while the K was measured by AAS (atomic absorption spectrophotometer). Base cations of soils were extracted with 1N NH₄COONH₃ pH7, and the contents of Ca, Mg, K, and Na in the extract were measured by AAS. Soil CEC is determined by ammonium acetate method pH 7 and EC_w of soil is measured by electrical conductivity meter. Soil fertility status

is assessed using five criteria of soil chemistry i.e. CEC, base saturation (BS), total P₂O₅, total K₂O, and organic C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Description of soil order

Fields observation of several soil orders including Inceptisol, Andisol, Mollisol, Ultisol, and Oxisol is presented in Table 1. The results align with what some studies have suggested about Aceh Besar's dryland, which showed that most of suboptimal soils were dominated by Inceptisols and Entisols (Sufardi *et al.*, 2017). Inceptisols generally develop from the parent material of clay sedimentary rocks and volcanic ash, while Andisols are found on the side of the volcanically active mountain (Seulawah Agam mount), whose mineral composition is an allophanic (amorphous mineral) group (Aceh Geological Map, 2016). Mollisols are found in a rather arid climate region in the northern part of Aceh Besar District with lime parent material (carst), which produces a soft and humus-rich soil matrix (Sufardi *et al.*, 2017). Oxisols originate from further weathering of old volcanic parent materials located at the bottom of Seulawah Agam mount. This soil order is sometimes found in association with Ultisols, Inceptisols and Andisols.

Table 1. Soil classification of some soil pedons in suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District according to the Soil Survey Staff (2014)

No. Pedon	Site/Village	Coordinate Point	Soil Classification
S1	Blang Bintang	05°36'58.41" N 95°47'51.82" E	Inceptisols (Oxic Haplustept, clayic, mixed, ferritic, isohyperthermic)
S2	Saree	05°06'58.41" N 95°27'51.82" E	Andisols (Eutric Hydrudand, medium, allophanic, isohyperthermic)
S3	Lembah Seulawah	05°27'19,4" N; 95°46'19,2" E	Oxisols (Plinthic Kandiudox, clayic, ferritic, isohyperthermic)
S4	Kreung Raya	05°36'36,6" N; 95°35'12,2" E	Mollisols (Typic Calcicaquolls, loamy, mixed, isohyperthermic)
S5	Jantho	05°16'58.41" N 95°37'51.82" E	Ultisols (Typic Kandiaquilt, clayic, kaolinitic, isohyperthermic)

Source: Field observation and laboratory analysis (2018)

Physical properties of soil

Table 2 shows that soil texture varies between soil type and horizons. Most of textural fraction are generally dominated by silt fraction. Silt fraction varied from 39-75%, clay from 11-49%, and the sand fraction is relatively smaller ranging from 6-29%. Based on field observations, the soil structure generally has blocky type in the upper layer and in the subsurface layer is dominated by subangular type. It also tends to be more massively structured with depth.

Table 2. Physical properties of soil at each horizon layer of several soil orders in suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District

Soil order	Horizon	Depth (cm)	Sand	Silt	Clay	Texture class	Soil Colour	Structure	Consistency (moist)
			----- (%) -----						
S1	AB	0 – 25	20	46	34	SL	10YR 5/6	Blocky	Crumbly
Inceptisol	BA	25 – 60	10	42	48	SL	7.5YR 5/8	Blocky	Soft
Blang Bintang	Bw	60 – 80	18	41	41	SL	5YR 4/8	Subangular	Soft
	Bob1	80-107	13	41	46	CL	5YR 5/6	Subangular	Hard
	Bob2	>107	9	46	45	SiL	7.5YR 5/6	Subangular	Hard
S2	Ap	0 – 20	14	59	27	SiL	7.7 YR 2/2	Crumb	Crumbly
Andisol	AB	20 – 38	13	61	26	SL	10 YR 2/3	Subangular	Soft
Saree	Bw	38 – 60	13	50	37	SiL	7.5 YR 3/4	Subangular	Crumbly
	BC	>60	17	67	16	SiL	7.5 YR 3/4	Subangular	Crumbly
S3	A	0 – 10	10	49	41	SiL	7.5 YR 4/4	Blocky	Crumbly
Oxisol	AB	10 – 35	9	65	26	SiL	7.5 YR 4/6	Subangular	Soft
Lb	BA	35-69	6	58	36	SiL	5 YR 4/4	Subangular	Soft
Seulawah	BO1	69-104	9	65	26	SiC	5 YR 4/8	Subangular	Hard
	BO2	104-150	10	45	45	C	5 YR 5/6	Subangular	Hard
S4	Ap	0-40	7	83	10	SiC	10 YR 1.7/1	Blocky	Soft
Mollisol	BA	40-75	6	83	11	CL	10 YR 3/2	Massive	Slightly hard
Kreung Raya	Bk1	75-110	6	83	11	LC	10 YR 4/3	Massive	Slightly hard
	Bk2	>110	6	75	16	C	10 YRR 5/2	Massive	Hard
S5	Ap	0 – 10	29	50	21	L	7.5 YR 5/6	Columnar	Soft
Ultisol	AB	10 – 27	18	57	25	CL	10 YR 5/6	Columnar	Slightly hard
Jantho	BA	27 – 45	14	60	25	CL	10 YR 6/6	Subangular	Slightly hard
	Bt1	45 – 97	13	54	33	CL	10 YR 7/1	Subangular	Slightly hard
	Bt2	97-125	12	39	49	C	10 YR 5/1	Subangular	Hard
	Bw2	>110	12	42	46	C	10 YR 5/1	Subangular	Hard

Sumber: Laboratory analysis and field observation (2018)

SL = sandy loam, CL = clay loam, SiL = silty loam, SiC= silty clay, C= clay, LC = loamy clay, L = Loam

Chemical Characteristics of Soil

Soil chemical characteristics in each horizon layer of the five soil orders are seen in Table 3.

Table 3. The value of pH, contents of total C, N, P₂O₅, and K₂O, and available P for each horizon layers of the soil orders in the suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District

Soil order	Horizon	Depth (cm)	pH H ₂ O	pH KCl	TOC TN		C/N	Total	Total	Available
					---(g kg ⁻¹) ---			P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	P (Bray II)
								--- (mg hg ⁻¹) -- (mg kg ⁻¹)		
S1	AB	0 – 25	5.44	4.41	9.9	0.7	14.1	101	20	1.05
Inceptisol	BA	25 – 60	5.36	4.48	8.2	0.6	13.7	53	25	1.55
Blang Bintang	Bw	60 – 80	5.83	5.20	4.5	0.5	9.00	78	103	1.75
	BOb1	80 – 107	6.00	5.49	3.7	0.4	9.25	66	6	1.15
	BOb2	>107	5.94	5.38	3.6	0.5	7.20	46	6	1.25
S2	Ap	0 - 20	5.30	4.25	44.4	2.7	16.4	83	5	2.50
Andisol	AB	20 - 38	5.56	4.35	39.5	2.5	15.8	213	72	2.50
Saree	Bw	38 - 60	5.87	4.69	14.2	1.4	10.1	754	4	3.00
	BC	>60	6.06	4.64	9.8	0.8	12.3	74	83	6.00
S3	A	0 – 10	5.25	4.09	9.4	0.8	11.8	87	49	1.75
Oxisol	AB	10 – 35	5.43	4.12	4.8	0.6	8.00	77	21	1.30
Lembah	BA	35 – 69	5.58	4.24	4.5	0.6	7.50	73	25	1.35
Seulawah	BO1	69 – 104	5.40	4.07	3.6	0.5	7.20	90	7	1.40
	BO2	104-150	5.36	4.00	3.4	0.5	6.80	64	6	5.50
S4	Ap	0-40	6.48	5.08	19.3	1.3	14.8	74	95	4.50
Mollisol	BA	40-75	8.35	6.66	12.9	1.4	7.25	83	157	5.00
Kreung Raya	Bk1	75-110	8.37	6.73	4.9	0.3	16.3	12	78	7.60
	Bk2	>110	8.44	6.77	3.2	0.4	8.00	29	166	12.5
S5	Ap	0 - 10	5.26	3.88	18.9	1.0	18.9	221	61	1.55
Ultisol	AB	10 – 27	5.97	4.00	5.3	0.4	13.3	156	79	1.45
Jantho	BA	27 – 45	6.34	4.53	4.4	0.4	11.0	129	59	2.85
	Bt1	45 - 97	6.41	4.65	3.7	0.4	9.25	230	66	2.00
	Bt2	97 - 125	6.60	4.74	2.3	0.3	7.67	37	5	1.50
	Bw2	>110	5.96	4.41	2.8	0.4	7.00	101	20	1.35

(1) Soil pH

Table 3 shows that pH H₂O and pH KCl in soils vary with soil orders and horizon layers (depth). In general, the actual pH or pH H₂O varies from acidic conditions (pH 5.25) to slightly alkaline (pH 8.44). The soils with acidic reaction were found on Inceptisols Blang Bintang, Andisols Saree, Oxisols Lembah Seulawah, and Ultisols Jantho whereas the soils with is neutral to slightly alkaline is found on Mollisols Krueng raya. The soil pH tends to increase with deeper depth. The tendency of increasing pH also happens in pH KCl, although the pH value is smaller than that of pH H₂O.

Based on these data, it can be concluded that the soils on suboptimal dryland in Aceh Besar District have a problem with soil acidity. Therefore, it is necessary to provide soils amendments that can reduce soil acidity, or by planting plants that are tolerant to soil acidity (Sanchez and Salinaz, 1982). Although most of soil orders included in acidic mineral soils (Sanchez, 2010), but no soil with extreme acidic pH or pH <4.50 found from the observations. This is also supported by

the results of exchangeable Al analysis (Al-exch), that the exchangeable Al in soil is relatively small and even there are of soils not contain of Al-exch (the data not presented). The low value of pH KCl compared to that of pH H₂O indicates that the soil in suboptimal dryland in the Aceh Besar district is classified into negatively charged soil (Uehara and Gillman, 1981).

(2) Total C and N content

Organic matter is an important component of an ideal soil system (Bohn *et al.*, 2010). The content of organic matter in mineral soils ranges 1.0 to 10%. Ideally, each soil should contain at least 5% organic matter, especially in the upper layers (FAO, 2005). Table 4 presents that the total C content in several soil orders varied from very low to high (2.3 to 39.5 g/kg C, or 4.6 to 79 Mg/ha). The total C content in suboptimal dryland areas in Aceh Besar District varies greatly with soil orders, although in general most of the area is dominated by soil with low C content. The soil orders containing low total C were found in Inceptisols Blang Bintang, Oxisols Lembah Seulawah, and Ultisols Jantho. Soils that contain medium total C were found in Mollisols Krueng Raya. High total C content soils were found in Andisols Saree. The soil C content also decreases with depth because of organic matter accumulation in the upper layer (horizon A) due to enrichment or melanization process (Stevenson 2010).

The low organic C in Inceptisols, Ultisols, and Oxisols is caused by its genesis. These three soils are formed from parent materials of sedimentary rocks or clay which lack in organic matter, in addition to the fact that these soils have been developed. Another reason is that these soils are formed in warm climate zones, which promotes rapid decomposition of organic matter and thus causes destruction of C from organic bonds to released carbon dioxide (Liski *et al.*, 1999; Stevenson, 2010; Sposito, 2008). Kirschbaum (1995) reported that the effects of temperature in the tropics can encourage the loss of C in the form of CO₂, causing global warming. This shows that the problem of scarcity of organic matter on suboptimal soil is a common case in wet tropical climates (Sanchez, 2010). The results of this study are consistent with reports in Sufardi *et al.* (2017) who stated that most of the soils in Aceh dryland has a low total C and N.

The organic matter content in soil reflects soil quality (Stevenson 2010) because they can directly or indirectly improve soil physical, chemical and biological properties (FAO, 2005; Sanchez, 2010; Sufardi, 2012). In most tropical climates zones, the soils contain a total C ranging from 1 to 5% (Bot and Benites, 2005). Therefore, efforts to maintain the balance of soil organic matter is a highly recommended in tropical soils especially on dryland (FAO, 2005; Sufardi *et al.*, 2017; Martunis *et al.*, 2017). Organic matter also functions as a source of nutrients, especially N, in which it can contain 3-10% (Nadi *et al.*, 2004). The results of this study also show that the total N content in soil is generally low

with range of 0.3 to 2.7 gkg N or equal to 0.6 to 5.4 Mg/ha. The available N content is relatively low, which range of 6 to 54 kg N/ha.

(3) Total P₂O₅, total K₂O, and available P

The P₂O₅ and K₂O extracted by 25% HCl are used as indicator of soil fertility, although this value does not always correlate with available forms (Sufardi, 2012). Table 3 shows that the content of P₂O₅ extracted by HCl 25% on topsoil in all soil orders was found to be sufficient because of its content > 20 mg/hg which included moderate to high criteria (29 mg to 740 mg/hg) or 0.58 to 1.48 Mg/ha. This data also shows that the total P₂O₅ content in suboptimal dryland in Aceh Besar District tends to vary in each type and also different in each layer of the horizon. This variation occurred because of difference of parent material, weathering level, climate, and the content P of soil (Mengel and Kikrby, 2010).

Table 3 also shows that available P (Bray II) in most soil orders, especially Inceptisols Blang Bintang, Andisols Saree, Oxisols Seulawah, and Ultisols Jantho is very low, ranging from 1.05 to 6.0 mg/kg or equivalent to 4.85 to 27.7 kg P₂O₅/ha. In Kreung Raya Mollisols, the P content is available slightly higher but is still relatively low at 4.5-12.5 mg/kg or 20.79 to 57.75 kg P₂O₅/ha. This shows that despite the total P content of the soil, it is relatively high but the P content is low. This is presumably because the soil found in Aceh Besar's suboptimal dryland area has high phosphate fixation. One indication is the presence of Andisols, Ultisols, and Oxisols soil orders which are known to have high P fixation so that they often cause P deficiency in cultivated plants (Sanchez, 2010). Andosols have high amorphous fractions that are highly reactive to phosphate so that the binding of P to this soil is very high, reaching even more than 92 percent (Mengel and Kikrby, 2010). The high P retention in Andisols is one of the characteristics of Andisols (Soil Survey Staff 2014). Low available P can be overcome by applying organic amendments and utilizing mycorrhizae to release P from minerals or binding (Karnilawati et al., 2013; Sufardi et al., 2013).

The total K₂O content in each soil type in Aceh Besar District's dryland varies greatly between the soil type (order) and horizon layer, and generally very low to very high, while the K-exch value of soil in each type of soil is almost uniform that is all included in the category is very low (<0.2 cmol/kg). Most of soils have enough phosphate and potassium reserves but the availability of potassium is very low. This is presumably because the source of K in the soil is an original minerals that are not easily decayed. This forms does not correlate directly with the release of K into the soil solution (Havlin *et al.*, 2010). To increase the solubility of K minerals can be overcome by adding

organic matter, because organic matter can dissolve soil minerals (Mengel and Kirby, 2010; Marschner, 2010).

(4) Exchange cations, CEC, BS and EC

The results of analysis showed that four soil orders (Inceptisols Blang Bintang, Andisols Saree, Oxisols Lembah Seulawah, and Ultisols Jantho) have low exchangeable cations (Ca, Mg, K, and Na), and only Mollisols Krueng Raya that has a high number of cations (Table 4). The exchangeable Ca in soils varies slightly between soil depths and it can classified as very low to low (0.71 to 8.32 cmol/kg). The Ca-exch at each horizon of Mollisols Krueng Raya were very high ranging from 29.8 to 44.3 cmol/kg in the deeper horizon.

Table 4. Exchangeable base cations, CEC, and BS at the horizon layers of the soil order in several horizons of suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District

Soil order	Horizon	Depth (cm)	Exchangeable base cations				Sum of cations	CEC	BS	EC
			Ca-exch	Mg-exch	K-exch	Na-exch				
			----- (cmol kg ⁻¹) -----							
								(%)		dS m ⁻¹
S1	AB	0 – 25	1.61	0.36	0.12	0.23	2.32	9.83	23.6	0.04
Inceptisol	BA	25 – 60	2.01	0.36	0.10	0.25	2.72	7.54	36.1	0.04
Blang	Bw	60 – 80	2.27	0.36	0.05	0.29	2.97	8.25	36.0	0.02
Bintang	BOb1	80 – 107	2.20	0.36	0.04	0.30	2.90	14.9	19.5	0.02
	BOb2	>107	2.44	0.36	0.03	0.31	3.14	8.12	38.7	0.02
S2	Ap	0 - 20	3.08	0.34	0.24	0.18	3.84	18.3	21.0	0.04
Andisol	AB	20 - 38	2.42	0.35	0.14	0.19	3.10	17.4	17.8	0.02
Saree	Bw	38 - 60	3.23	0.36	0.38	0.21	4.18	20.9	20.0	0.01
	BC	>60	4.14	0.36	0.19	0.22	4.91	23.5	20.9	0.02
S3	A	0 – 10	2.05	0.36	0.19	0.20	2.80	14.4	19.4	0.05
Oxisol	AB	10 – 35	1.74	0.35	0.03	0.19	2.31	12.6	18.3	0.02
Lembah	BA	35 – 69	1.89	0.36	0.05	0.21	2.51	13.1	19.2	0.02
Seulawah	BO1	69 – 104	1.77	0.36	0.03	0.23	2.39	14.1	17.0	0.03
	BO2	104-150	1.56	0.36	0.03	0.24	2.19	13.4	16.3	0.02
S4	Ap	0-40	29.8	0.37	0.37	0.35	30.89	52.6	58.7	0.17
Mollisol	BA	40-75	41.7	0.39	0.30	0.38	42.77	61.5	69.5	0.30
Krueng Raya	Bk1	75-110	44.2	0.39	0.24	0.42	45.25	62.5	72.4	0.40
	Bk2	>110	43.6	0.38	0.29	0.41	44.68	59.8	74.7	0.30
S5	Ap	0 - 10	4.00	0.38	0.21	0.41	5.00	14.7	34.0	0.05
Ultisol	AB	10 – 27	7.57	0.37	0.19	0.42	8.55	36.0	23.8	0.05
Jalin	BA	27 – 45	4.35	0.38	0.17	0.42	5.32	33.5	15.9	0.07
	Bt1	45 - 97	8.32	0.38	0.12	0.39	9.21	30.9	29.8	0.04
	Bt2	97 - 125	0.71	0.39	0.17	0.40	1.67	36.9	4.50	0.06

The levels of Mg-exch in all soil orders were very low (<0.40 cmol/kg), while K-exch varied from very low to moderate (0.03-0.38 cmol/kg). The availability of exchangeable cations especially Ca, Mg, and K in dryland soils at Aceh Besar is generally limited and this becomes a constraints for plant growth especially in the order of Inceptisols, Andisols, Oxisols and Ultisols, but availability of Ca, Mg, and K in Mollisols is relatively high. The deficiency of

Ca, Mg, and K can inhibit plant growth (Havlin *et al.*, 2010; Marschner, 2010; Mengel and Kirkby, 2010; Sufardi, 2012). Table 4 also shows that the levels of Na-exch at each horizon of the five soil orders are categorized as very low to low (0.18-0.42 cmol/kg) and relatively not so different between soil orders. This shows that there is no indication of the influence of salt (Na) on soils in suboptimal land of Aceh Besar. The low levels of Na-exch are also reflected in EC value which is also very low (0.01-0.17 dS/m).

The most of soils in the dryland area of Aceh Besar District (Inceptisols, Andisols, Oxisols, and Ultisols) have a low sum of cations because it is less than 10 cmol/kg, except in Mollisols Krueng Raya. In the Mollisols Krueng Raya, sum of cations ranges 30.89 to 45.25 cmol/kg, which means that this soil is better quality than other soils. Table 4 also shows that the value of soil CEC on suboptimal dryland in Aceh Besar District varies between types of soil and between layers of horizon. In Inceptisols Blang Bintang, CEC varied from 7.4 to 14.9 cmol/kg (low), Andisols Saree varied from 17.4-23.5 cmol/kg (moderate), Oxisols Lembah Seulawah ranged from 12.6 -14.4 cmol/kg (low), Mollisols Krueng Raya varies from 52.6-62.5 cmol/kg (very high), and Ultisols Jantho varies from 14.7 to 36.9 cmol/kg (low to high). Based on the CEC value of soils, the highest to lowest CEC sequence is Mollisols > Ultisols > Andisols > Oxisols > Inceptisols. Base saturation (BS) of soils also varies between soil orders and horizons (depth), but the soils in suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar have low base saturation (<35%) for the Inceptisols, Andisols, Ultisols, and Oxisols, but in Mollisols Krueng Raya, the percentage of base saturation is high (> 50%). Based on this data, it can be said that low BS value of soils is one of constraint in suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District, because the BS value reflects the number of exchanged cations that occupy soil colloids (Bohn *et al.*, 2010).

Status of Soil Fertility

Assessment soil fertility status in suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District shows that the soil fertility could be divided into two categories, namely low and medium soil fertility status (Table 5). Soil orders with low fertility include Inceptisols Blang Bintang, Oxisols Lembah Seulawah, and Ultisols Jantho, while a medium category are Andisols Saree and Mollisol sKrueng Raya. Low fertility in dryland soils had been reported by Martunis *et al.* (2017). The low soil fertility status on drylands of Aceh Besar due to several limiting factors such as low organic matter content, low CEC, low base saturation, and low exchangeable cations.

Table 5. Soil fertility status of several soil orders on suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District

Soil fertility parameters	Inceptisols Blang Bintang	Andisols Saree	Oxisols Lembah Seulawah	Mollisols Krueng Raya	Ultisols Jantho
pH (H ₂ O)	5.44 ^A	5.30 ^A	5.25 ^A	6.48 ^{SA}	5.26 ^A
C-Organic (Walkley & Black, g/kg)	9.90 ^L	44.4 ^H	9.40 ^L	19.3 ^L	18.9 ^L
P ₂ O ₅ total (HCl 25%, mg/100g)	101.0 ^H	83.0 ^H	87.0 ^H	74.0 ^H	221 ^H
K ₂ O total (HCl 25%, mg/100g)	22.0 ^M	5.0 ^L	49.0 ^H	95.0 ^H	61.0 ^H
CEC 1N NH ₄ COOCH ₃					
pH7 (cmol/kg)	9.83 ^L	18.3 ^M	14.4 ^L	52.6 ^H	14.7 ^L
Base saturation (%)	23.6 ^L	21.0 ^L	19.4 ^L	58.7 ^H	34.0 ^L
Soil fertility status	low	medium	low	mediu m	low

Notes: A/SA = acid/slightly acid; L/M/H = low/medium/high

Organic matter is critical for the soil to maintain its fertility and productivity. Bohn *et al.* (2010) stated that organic matter greatly affects the value of soil CEC and a source of energy for soil microorganism. Organic matter has an positive effect on cation exchange capacity, nutrient availability, serves as a buffer against changes in pH, and provides plant nutrient supplies (Stevenson, 2010; Marschner, 2012). Therefore, it is necessary to add organic matters for improving soil quality and fertility status. Sufardi (2012) states that organic matters should be added because soil organic matter is very important to create fertile conditions of soil. Sposito (2008) explained that organic matter can increase CEC up about 20-70% and as the main source of humus colloid formation (Sufardi 2012). Besides CEC and organic C, soil base saturation is always associated with soil fertility. Based on this research, Inceptisols, Oxisols and Ultisols with catagorized as infertile soils while Mollisols and Andisols categorized as fertile soils.

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) Physical andl chemical characteristics of suboptimal dryland of Aceh Besar District vary depend on soil orders and soil horizons. This difference is caused by the different parent materials and the process of soil genesis.

From the chemical aspects, the main problem of the soil are low soil pH, low N, P, K, Ca, and Mg nutrients, and low organic material.

- (2) The low fertility belongs to Inceptisols Blang Bintang, Oxisols Lembah Seulawah, and Ultisols Jantho, whereas Andisols Saree and Mollisols Krueng Raya are classified as soils with medium fertility. The order of soil fertility from the highest to lowest is: Mollisols = Andisols > Ultisols = Oxisols = Inceptisols.
- (3) The main limiting factor in suboptimal dryland in Aceh Besar District is acid soil reaction, low organic C, low CEC, and low base saturation (BS). To improve their quality and fertility status, it is necessary to add ameliorants, biofertilizers, biochar, and fertilizers.

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